

THE PENETRATION BEHAVIOUR OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present some analytical models for the penetration of GFRP by projectiles, and the results of some penetration experiments. The materials considered include a family of E-glass/polyester composites, and two S2-glass/phenolic materials. Quasi-static indentation tests and ballistic depth-of-penetration tests have been undertaken, and the work done by the GFRP in each instance has been estimated. The work done under ballistic rates was found to be comparable with the quasi-static value. A stress wave propagation model to describe the penetration of GFRP by a blunt projectile is also presented, and this shows good agreement with experimental results.

INTRODUCTION

The use of glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) for ballistic protection is well established and there are a number of military vehicles in service around the world containing GFRP armour. GFRPs can offer a significant weight saving over some other materials, and are currently used as spall liners and in the protection of bank staff.

Several authors have studied the ballistic performance of GFRP. However, to date, attempts to correlate their ballistic performance with laminate construction or material properties has achieved only limited, qualitative success [1,2,3,4]. The failure mechanisms of GFRPs have been studied in some cases [1,3], but these have not been linked in any quantitative way to the materials' ballistic performance. Also, several quantitative models have been proposed to describe the ballistic performance [4], but these do not take into account the complex nature of the composite failure modes.

The work covered in this paper is part of a programme whose purpose is to fully characterise the energy absorption and fracture behaviour of these materials under penetration conditions.

In an earlier paper [5], GFRP undergoing normal ballistic impact by a fragment simulating projectile (FSP) was studied, and two distinct failure modes were identified. These were described as Phase I and II (see figure 1.).

- Phase I represents the initial penetration at the front surface and includes localised crushing of fibres and resin, shearing of fibres and expulsion of this debris. This phase has been shown to absorb most of the projectile kinetic energy.

- Phase II initiates part way through the GFRP material. Phase I gives way to a 'cone' of delaminated layers in which the delamination radius increases reaching a maximum at the rear surface of the material.

Figure 1. Penetration of GFRP

In this paper we concentrate on Phase I failure of GFRP. Phase I penetration experiments have been performed at both quasi-static and ballistic rates, and correlations have been made between the results, in terms of energy absorption calculations and physical fracture behaviour. Phase I has been isolated from phase II by fully supporting the rear face of the GFRP, thus preventing delamination. In both the quasi-static and ballistic experiments, similar materials and penetrators have been used to allow valid comparison of the results.

This paper also includes an analytical model to describe the phase I penetration of a blunt indenter into GFRP. This model is based on stress wave propagation through the materials and, so far, has achieved good agreement with the available experimental results.

QUASI-STATIC INDENTATION TESTS

In these tests the specimen, a plate of GFRP, was supported on the lower platen of an Instron test machine. The indenter, which was one of the projectiles for use in the ballistic tests, was pushed down into the specimen by the upper platen of the test machine. Various indentors were used, including: the steel core of a 0.3" calibre armour piercing (AP) round, steel cylinders with 90° conical tips (0.3" and 0.5" diameter) and blunt cylinders (0.3" and 0.5"), which could be considered cones of angle 180°. The AP round has an ogival pointed nose, i.e. the included angle gradually increases from 0° at the sides to 90° at the central point. The displacement rate was 0.1 mm/s.

The resulting load-displacement curves were integrated to calculate the work done during penetration. However, as the GFRP plates were supported on a compression platen, complete perforation was not achieved. In order to allow direct correlation with the ballistic tests, it was necessary to extrapolate the load-displacement data to include perforation of the GFRP and exit of the penetrator. Therefore, certain assumptions were necessary to describe the total penetration and perforation load-displacement behaviour and these were different for each penetrator type.

0.3" AP ROUNDS

For these rounds the load-displacement curve showed an initial increase in load with displacement as the ogival head penetrated the material. The curve then levelled off as the constant diameter section penetrated. The load-displacement curve has been extrapolated to include the perforation behaviour by simply extending this plateau of the curve to a displacement equivalent to the GFRP thickness + ogival head height.

CONICAL INDENTATION TESTS

The load-displacement curves for the conical indentors were found to have a parabolic increase in load with displacement. The indentation law is therefore of the following form, where the coefficient k depends on the material tested and the cone angle.

ie:

$$\text{load} = k \cdot (\text{displacement})^2 \qquad k = \text{constant}$$

Once the conical head had fully indented the GFRP, the curve levelled off, and there was no further increase in load as the constant diameter section penetrated the material.

An approximation has been derived [6] to describe the total load-displacement behaviour of a conical indentation test. The curve (see figure 2.) can be split into three stages, each representing a different part of the indentation process.

Figure 2. Indentation of GFRP by a conical indenter

- A Initial parabolic loading as the conical head enters the GFRP, as observed during experiments.
- B The constant diameter section of the indenter enters the GFRP, accompanied by no variation in load.
- C At this point, the conical head perforates the rear face. It is assumed that the load decreases parabolically in the same way as it increased initially.

As can be seen in figure 2, the geometry of this resulting curve allows the work done to be calculated simply by multiplying the peak load by the thickness of the GFRP.

BLUNT INDENTATION TESTS

The load-displacement behaviour consisted of a linear increase in load with displacement, until the gradient decreased producing a more gradual increase in load with displacement. The curve was extrapolated by extending this curve, until the displacement equalled the thickness of the GFRP. Indentation using the 0.5" blunt fragment was not possible as the platens could have been damaged due to the higher loads anticipated.

Some of the results from this work are summarised below in table 3.

energy absorbed J			
0.3" AP round	0.3" conical	0.5" conical	0.3" blunt
547	1468	1561	1314

Table 3. Indentation Energies for 15 mm Thick Plate of Structural S2-glass/Phenolic

RESIDUAL DEPTH-OF-PENETRATION TESTS

These tests allow the energy absorbed by GFRP during ballistic penetration to be estimated. This is achieved by measuring the residual depth of penetration (DOP) of the projectile into high density polyethylene (HDPE) blocks which are used to back the GFRP. By comparing these DOP values with depth of penetration data for HDPE alone, an estimation can be made of how much equivalent DOP the GFRP represents. By plotting the DOP data against kinetic energy, this value can be translated into the energy absorbed by the GFRP. Two trials were undertaken, using different projectiles.

0.3" AP ROUNDS

In the first trial [7] 0.3" AP rounds were used. These rounds consist of a steel core with a soft copper jacket. It was necessary to strip the copper jacket prior to penetration, to ensure only the steel core entered the GFRP. A 15 mm GFRP panel was positioned 25 mm in front of the target panel to strip the jacket.

Two different GFRP target arrangements were used. In the first arrangement, spacers were used with a span of 150 mm to separate the GFRP from the HDPE. This was to allow both phase I and phase II penetration behaviour to occur, ie both crushing and delamination modes were possible. In the second arrangement the GFRP was firmly clamped to the HDPE, preventing rear face delamination from occurring, ie phase II is inhibited.

Supported GFRP

The resulting depth-of-penetration-kinetic energy curves from this work were linear and parallel to a good degree of accuracy. The resulting values measured for the energy absorbed by the GFRP under phase I penetration correlated well with the quasi-static results. See table 4 (NB, each material was of a different thickness therefore comparison between the materials cannot be made.)

Unsupported GFRP

The energy absorbed in the unsupported GFRP tests, ie including phase II failure, was found to be significantly lower than energy absorbed by the supported GFRP, in all cases for all FRPs. For example, for structural grade S2-glass/phenolic GFRP, 541 Joules were absorbed in the supported material, whereas only 480 J was calculated for the unsupported material. This consistent observation demonstrates that against pointed projectiles, GFRPs absorb more kinetic energy when fully

supported.

Material	Work Done J (quasi-static)	Energy Absorbed J (DOP test)	WD(QS)/E(DOP)
E/polyester Wf*=0.5	406	428	0.95
E/polyester Wf=0.6	465	455	1.02
E/polyester Wf=0.7	537	504	1.07
E/polyester Wf=0.8	509	473	1.08
S2/phenolic structural	547	541	1.01
S2/phenolic ballistic	542	461	1.18

Table 4. Comparison of quasi-static and ballistic penetration of supported GFRP by 0.3" AP rounds
(*Wf = fibre weight fraction)

CONICAL AND BLUNT FRAGMENTS

In this trial [8] similar experiments were carried out, except conical and blunt fragments were used and there was no need to strip jackets with a separate plate. Fragments the same size and shape as those used in the quasi-static work were manufactured and these were heat treated to Hv 720 to prevent deformation during the tests. As these fragments were hardened, sabots were used to launch the fragments. These sabots separated during flight and therefore did not affect the penetration behaviour.

As before the fragments were fired, over a range of velocities, into GFRP firmly clamped to HDPE blocks, and also into the HDPE in order to collect reference data. In all the tests the conical fragments resisted deformation, however the hardened blunt fragments did exhibit some deformation at the highest velocities. Surprisingly, the DOP-KE curves (figure 5) for the blunt fragments were parallel, whereas the curves for the conical fragments diverged in one instance and converged in another. The curves have been plotted below with linear regression approximations.

Unfortunately, for the 0.3" blunt fragments the HDPE-only line intersects the DOP axis at about 30 mm. This implies that a stationary fragment will penetrate the HDPE about 30 mm, which is clearly incorrect. Further work will be carried out to determine the behaviour as the velocities tend toward zero.

Mean energy values have been calculated for these results, and these have been compared with the quasi-static results in table 6. These values do not correlate as well as the results from the AP round experiments. Some of the differences may be due to small deformations of the fragments in the DOP tests, but the errors inherent in using linear extrapolation of the DOP data are probably a major factor.

Figure 5. Residual Depth-of-Penetration tests results.

Projectile	Work Done (quasi-static indentation test) J	Energy Absorbed (Ballistic DOP test) J
0.3" Conical	1468	1201
0.3" Blunt	1314	1897
0.5" Conical	1561	1901
0.5" Blunt		1371

Table 6. Comparison of quasi-static and ballistic penetration energies

ANALYTICAL MODEL TO DESCRIBE THE PENETRATION OF A GFRP BY A BLUNT PROJECTILE

This model [9] describes phase I, ie crushing of target material and its ejection behind a blunt projectile. It uses stress wave propagation as a basis for describing the behaviour. It extends a model in which acoustic impedances were used to calculate projectile velocity change on impact[10]. One limitation of the acoustic impedance model is that the calculated stress exceeds the strength of the material. This new model therefore allows for target erosion.

In this model, both the projectile and the target are treated as rods. On impact a stress wave is initiated in the target, and a stress wave also travels back through the projectile. If both materials remain elastic then both attain the same particle velocity v and stress wave amplitude σ . These two are related by :

$$\sigma = \rho_t c_t v \tag{1}$$

where ρ_t and c_t are the density and wave speed in the target respectively. However, the amplitude of the stress induced in the target is limited to a characteristic value; the erosion stress σ_2 . The limit on stress means that target's particle velocity is also limited, to v_2 , via Eqn (2), which is essentially the same as Eqn (1).

$$\sigma_2 = \rho_t c_t v_2 \tag{2}$$

The corresponding equation for the projectile is :

$$\sigma_p = \rho_p c_p (v_0 - v_1) \tag{3}$$

where v_0 is the initial velocity and v_1 that after the stress wave has passed. Normally, $v_1 > v_2$, the projectile front moves faster than the target, and the target is eroded. It is assumed that the eroded material is accelerated up to v_1 and then escapes as it cannot occupy the same space as the projectile. This acceleration produces an extra stress σ_e , given by:

$$\sigma_e = (v_1 - v_2)^2 \rho_t \tag{4}$$

Any frictional effects of the debris passing back behind the projectile are neglected. Stress balance at the front of the projectile requires that

$$\sigma_p = \sigma_e + \sigma_2 \tag{5}$$

and this system of equations can be solved. At this point there are stress waves travelling through both projectile and target and the target is being eroded. The stress wave in the projectile is reflected as an unloading wave at the rear surface, and this release wave eventually passes into the target, unloading it and reducing the particle velocity to zero.

Figure 7. Stress wave propagation model

The projectile, now with a reduced velocity, then strikes the target again and reloads it. As before the stress waves pass through projectile and target and further erosion takes place. These cycles repeat until the stress wave is elastic and no further erosion occurs. Two sets of experimental results have been compared with this model.

The first uses data presented by Woodward and Egglestone [11]. Initially, indentation tests were done on a GFRP under quasi-static conditions and at high strain rate in a split Hopkinson bar (SHPB). In the SHPB tests the average stress was 570 MPa; therefore this value was taken as the erosion stress for the model. These authors then fired a hard steel cylinder at a thick plate of the GFRP at 330 m/s. This resulted in a depth of penetration of 9 mm. Using the erosion model, a DOP of 9.6 mm was predicted, which is a remarkably good agreement.

Our own experimental programme involved DOP tests in which chisel-nosed FSPs were fired into semi-infinite GFRP. Although these projectiles were neither flat ended nor undeforming and we had

not measured the erosion stress of the GFRP, the model produced a very similar trend in results. By setting the erosion stress to 550 MPa, the results could be made to agree very well.

Figure 8. Comparison of experimental results and the stress wave propagation model

CONCLUSIONS

This work has demonstrated methods to estimate the work done by a GFRP during perforation both at quasi-static and ballistic velocities. It has also shown that the work done at quasi-static rates is comparable to the work done during ballistic rates of penetration and, in fact, the results from the armour piercing projectiles suggest that these two energies are close to being equal. This could not be confirmed with the conical projectiles because of difficulties associated with the method of estimating the absorbed energy, but additional work is in hand to overcome them. The erosion model for predicting the behaviour of a GFRP being penetrated by a blunt projectile has also produced promising results, although comparison with more experiments will be necessary before its validity can be confidently established.

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